

KESULITAN SISWA SEKOLAH MENENGAH PERTAMA DALAM MENYELESAIKAN SOAL MATEMATIKA PISA-LIKE

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Abstrak

PISA merupakan program internasional yang diselenggarakan oleh OECD dengan tujuan mengevaluasi kemampuan anak usia 15 tahun pada membaca, matematika, dan sains. Penelitian termasuk dalam penelitian kualitatif dengan tujuan untuk mendeskripsikan kesulitan siswa dalam menyelesaikan soal matematika PISA-Like. Sampel penelitian sebanyak 46 siswa SMP di Kota Surakarta yang dipilih dengan teknik *simple random sampling*. Instrumen penelitian terdiri dari tes berupa soal matematika PISA-Like dan nontes berupa angket. Analisis data dilakukan melalui reduksi data, penyajian data, verifikasi, dan penarikan kesimpulan. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa siswa mengalami kesulitan dalam menyelesaikan soal PISA-Like. Beberapa hal yang menyebabkan kesulitan siswa dalam menyelesaikan soal PISA-Like, yaitu: kurangnya pemahaman siswa terhadap soal yang diberikan; stimulus soal yang panjang dan rumit; serta tidak mengetahui konsep matematika yang akan digunakan. Kurangnya pemahaman siswa terhadap soal karena belum terbiasa menghadapi soal PISA sehingga mengalami kebingungan menggunakan konsep matematika.

Kata Kunci: kesulitan siswa; literasi matematika; PISA-Like.

Abstract

PISA is an international program organized by OECD aiming at evaluating the reading, mathematical, and science skills of students 15 years of age. This qualitative research attempted to describe students' difficulty in solving PISA mathematic questions. To this end, forty-six junior high school students in Surakarta were involved with simple random sampling. The instruments in this research consisted of test instruments in the form of PISA-Like math problems and nontest instruments in the form of questionnaires. Data analysis was carried out through data reduction, data presentation, verification, and drawing conclusions. The results showed that students had difficulty solving PISA-Like questions. Several factors were found to account for students' difficulty in solving PISA-Like questions, including their poor understanding of the question; the long and complex stimulus of the question; and their lack of knowledge of the mathematical concept to be used. Students' poor understanding of the question was particularly attributed to their unfamiliarity with questions, causing them to be confused about the mathematical concept to use.

Keywords: student difficulties; mathematical literacy; PISA-Like.